

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AKHILA K Sbearing USN 6SU19AO001 has completed his/her internship at Kasturba medical college Manipal in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ALEENA CATHERIN bearing USN 6SU19AO002 has completed his/her internship at Kasturba medical college Manipal

in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANAGHA UNNIKRISHNAN bearing USN 6SU19AO003 has completed his/her internship at Kasturba medical college Manipal in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ARSHA PURUSHOTHAMAN bearing USN 6SU19AO004 has completed his/her internship at Kasturba medical college Manipal in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ASHLY SHAJI bearing USN 6SU19AO005 has completed his/her internship at Kasturba medical college Manipal

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ASWIN DEV N Sbearing USN 6SU19AO006has completed his/her internship at Kasturba medical college Manipal

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms DRISHYA S DAMODARAN bearing USN 6SU19AO007 has completed his/her internship at Kasturba medical college Manipal in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms FATHIMA S BASHEER bearing USN 6SU19AO008 has completed his/her internship at Kasturba medical college Manipal

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms HARITHA MURALI bearing USN 6SU19AO009 has completed his/her internship at Kasturba medical college Manipal

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms JAISON M SIMON bearing USN 6SU19AO010 has completed his/her internship at Kasturba medical college Manipal

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms JEFFIN JOHNSON bearing USN 6SU19AO011 has completed his/her internship at Kasturba medical college Manipal

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms JOJO JOSE bearing USN 6SU19AO012 has completed his/her internship at Kasturba medical college Manipal

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms JOYICE JOHNSON bearing USN 6SU19A0013 has completed his/her internship at Kasturba medical college Manipal

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms K.SNEHA bearing USN 6SU19A0014 has completed his/her internship at Kasturba medical college Manipal

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms KEVIN SIMON bearing USN 6SU19AO015 has completed his/her internship at Kasturba medical college Manipal

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MEENU S DEV bearing USN 6SU19A0016 has completed his/her internship at Kasturba medical college Manipal

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMMED NASIH P T bearing USN 6SU19AO017 has completed his/her internship at Kasturba medical college Manipal

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